

Stochastically averaged subdynamics of two-level systems (TLS) coupled to a colored noise : a nonperturbative time-ordered cluster cumulant method[†]

Sheikh Hannan Mandal^a, Rathindranath Ghosh^b and Debashis Mukherjee^{*c}

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-Mail : pcdm@mahendra.iacs.res.in

^aPresent address : Department of Physical Science, R. K. M. Sikshanamandira, Belurmath, Howrah-711 202, India

^bPresent address : Department of Chemistry, R. K. M. Residential College, Narendrapur, Kolkata-700 103, India

^cAlso at : Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research, Bangalore-560 064, India

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We present here a non-perturbative cumulant expansion method of studying stochastically averaged dynamics of a TLS coupled to a gaussian colored noise bath. It uses a factorized cluster Ansatz for the evolution operator, $U(t)$ suggested in an earlier formalism (Ref. 22). The factorization separates the operators involving only the system variables from those containing the intractions involving the bath variables. The stochastically averaged $U(t)$ is obtained in a compact way by way of introducing bath-normal ordered products, which have zero bath averages for the bath-variables satisfying gaussian factorization property. We use a Wick-like operator reordering theorem (Ref. 25) to have a bath-normal ordered cluster expansion representation of $U(t)$ and subsequently Novikov's theorem (Ref. 27) to get equations for the cluster amplitudes without free bath variables. The subdynamics of the system where the bath-variables are averaged out is governed in our method by a time-local effective hamiltonian involving system variables only. The method is efficacious when the bath is strongly colored and its coupling with the system is strong, e.g. when nonperturbative effects are prominent. The efficacy of the method is illustrated by computing power spectra from a model system which mimics nonadiabatic vibronic coupling simulated by colored noise.

The study of real-time dynamics of a two-level system (TLS) coupled to a bath continues to be of considerable interest because of its underlying richness and potentiality to mimic a diverse range of phenomena¹⁻³. With the increased time resolution achieved in spectroscopy in the recent years, it has become feasible to monitor real-time dynamics for ultrafast processes³⁻⁶. The nontrivial evolution pattern of a system coupled to a bath can be now studied by probing the ultrafast processes where the relaxation time, t_r of the system to be probed is of the order of the correlation time, τ_c of the bath. A microscopic quantum mechanical description of the reservoir usually consists of a system of harmonic oscillators^{8,9}. There are attempts to simulate the microscopic effect of the bath by the stochastic bath via the correlation function of the classical bath variable^{10,11} where the bath mode possesses gaussian factorization property¹². Such a situation may ideally be simulated by colored noise – particularly of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) variety¹.

The most well-known and widely used strategies of averaging of the bath degrees of freedom in such a system-bath problem is via perturbative cumulant expansion and

the related methods^{13,14}, the partial summation of a set of important terms of the perturbative cumulant expansion scheme^{10,11}, the projection operator techniques^{15,16} leading to 'time-retarded memory kernel', the Fokker-Planck formalism involving marginal averages¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and the path-integral based methods^{4,7-9,20,21}. Based on our time-dependent generalization of the multireference coupled cluster (TDMRCC) formalism²², we have developed recently a nonperturbative cluster expansion method^{23,24} for 'stochastic averaging' of the time evolution operator, $U(t)$ for quantum systems driven by OU colored noise. The efficacy of the TDMRCC approach lies in its non-perturbative character, which affords a convenient access to study bath-averaged subdynamics of the system driven by strongly colored noise. We called this development a nonperturbative cluster cumulant method in our earlier papers. The bath variables were mapped there to a system of bosons, and the stochastic averaging was simplified by writing the interaction hamiltonian in terms of normal ordered products with respect to the 'bath bosons'.

In this paper, we explore an alternative cluster cumulant

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

approach by introducing a different time-ordered exponential Ansatz for the evolution operator, $U(t)$. This approach is useful when the system consists of several levels (non necessarily bosons or fermions) and the bath variables satisfy gaussian factorization property. Unlike in Refs. 23,24, here we can thus normal order only the bath variables, but system variables cannot be ordered in a similar manner. Also, in the present approach, we have treated the stochastic variables $f(t)$ as just some field variables rather mapping them to 'bath-boson' variables. We invoke the concepts of normal ordering of the products of $f(t)$'s and contraction of $f(t)$ variables²⁵, introduced earlier by us for performing the average of the time-ordered products of $f(t)$ variables. Bath averaged values of normal products of $f(t)$ variables are taken as zero^{24,25} by definition and the two-time correlation function of two f 's is taken to be OU variety. We treat in our example application as having two levels, so operators involving the system variables are 2×2 matrix. From the mode of development of the method, as expounded in the next section, it would be clear that the number of levels need not be confined to two, e.g. the method is quite general.

Time ordered cluster cumulant approach for the TLS-bath problem : the formalism

Time-dependent Bloch equation in the theory of subdynamics : a resumé :

Let us consider a generic TLS-bath hamiltonian of the form,

$$H(t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 [\epsilon_i + g_{ij} f(t)] |i\rangle\langle i| + \sum_{i \neq j=1}^2 [\gamma_{ij} + g_{ij} f(t)] |i\rangle\langle j| \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_i and γ_{ij} are deterministic hamiltonian matrix-elements of the system variables and g_{ij} and g_{ij} denote stochastic coupling constants. $f(t)$ is a classical probability-distribution valued stochastic variable which satisfies the following stationary Gaussian distribution properties :

$$\langle f(t) \rangle = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (2)$$

$$\langle f(t_1) f(t_2) \rangle = G(t_1, t_2) = \frac{\lambda}{2} e^{-\lambda |t_1 - t_2|} \quad (3)$$

$$\langle f(t_1) \dots f(t_{2n}) \rangle = \sum_{\text{all}(n)\text{pairs}} IK f(t_1) f(t_2) \quad (4)$$

$$\langle f(t_1) \dots f(t_{2n+1}) \rangle = 0 \quad (5)$$

The two-time correlation function eq. (3) above, has been normalized to unit area for the integral over all times. $f(t)$ is

clearly a colored noise of the OU type. The bath correlation time $\tau_c \sim 1/\gamma$.

The Heisenberg's equation of motion for the system-bath complex is given by

$$i \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}^H(t)}{\partial t} = H(t) \mathcal{U}^H(t) \quad (6)$$

By partitioning the total hamiltonian, H into an unperturbed part H_0 and a perturbation part V , we can rewrite eqn. (6) as

$$i \frac{\partial U(t)}{\partial t} = V(t) U(t) \quad (7)$$

where $V(t) = e^{iH_0 t} V e^{-iH_0 t}$ and $U(t) = e^{iH_0 t} \mathcal{U}^H(t)$. We posit on $U(t)$ a factorization Ansatz of the following form²²⁻²⁴,

$$U(t) \equiv U_{\text{ex}}(t) U_M(t) \quad (8)$$

$U_M(t)$ involves evolution only within the system space, which we call the *model space* and $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ brings in the contribution from the bath-coupling. $U_M(t)$ thus contains system variables only, while $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ has in addition bath variables as well.

We also introduce the projector P onto the model space. Q is the complementary projector involving both the system and the bath degrees of freedom. We can then classify all the operators as 'model' and 'external' depending on whether involve respectively only system variables or both system and bath-variables. Then for any operator A , $PA = A_M$ and $QA = A_{\text{ex}}$. We have shown²²⁻²⁴ that this Ansatz leads to a *rigorous decoupling* of the evolution equation for $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ and $U_M(t)$, which allows us to study the subdynamics of the stochastically averaged $U(t)$, $\langle U(t) \rangle$ in terms of $U_M(t)$ only :

$$\langle U(t) \rangle \equiv PU(t)P = U_M(t) \quad (9)$$

Without going into detailed derivation, we are just quoting here the final forms of the time evolution equations for $U_M(t)$ and $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$. Substituting eqn. (8) in eqn. (7) and subsequent P projection leads to the time evolution equation for the model operator $U_M(t)$ governed by the effective system hamiltonian, $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ and is given by

$$i \frac{\partial U_M(t)}{\partial t} = V_{\text{eff}}(t) U_M(t) \quad (10)$$

$V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ is necessarily defined in the system space only and explicitly given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(t) = [PU_{\text{ex}}(t)P]^{-1} \left[PV(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t)P - iP \frac{\partial U_{\text{ex}}(t)}{\partial t} \right] \quad (11)$$

It may be noted that $PU_{\text{ex}}(t)P$ is a quantity at our disposal whose time-variation has to be fixed from outside. Although various types of normalization have been discussed in the literature²⁶, here we fix it via positing $PU_{\text{ex}}(t)P = P$. Then $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ is given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(t) = PV(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t)P \quad (12)$$

This indicates that $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ in eq. (11) depends entirely on $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ and not on $U_{\text{M}}(t)$. Thus our factorized Ansatz leads to a decoupling of the equation for $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ from that of $U_{\text{M}}(t)$. Similarly, plugging eq. (8) in eq. (7) and subsequent Q projection leads to the desired evolution equation for $QU_{\text{ex}}(t)P$ and is given by

$$i\frac{\partial QU_{\text{ex}}(t)}{\partial t} = QV(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t) - QU_{\text{ex}}(t)V_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (13)$$

Having solved for $QU_{\text{ex}}(t)P$, given a $PU_{\text{ex}}(t)P$, we can solve for $U_{\text{M}}(t)$ by substituting eq. (11) in eqn. (10) which we call the time-dependent Bloch equation²²⁻²⁴. The factorization Ansatz for $U(t)$ immediately leads to one property for $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ which we seek, viz. $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ depends on time via just one time-argument, since it is determined by an equation for $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ obtained by solving a first order differential equation in time. This convenient aspect should be contrasted with all the approaches using memory kernel^{15,16} and the path-integral based strategies using influence functionals^{4,8,9,20,21}, which are nonlocal in time and are hence much harder to solve.

We emphasize here that the relation, $PU_{\text{ex}}(t)P = P$ is essential for us to arrive at the simple expression of $\langle U(t) \rangle$ in eq. (9). This is realized in our formalism by rewriting all operators containing the bath variables in normal ordered product form for the bath variables²⁵. By definition, the averages of operators in bath normal ordered forms have zero stochastic averages over the bath variables : $\langle A(t) \rangle \equiv PA(t)P \equiv 0$. Thus, if we express $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$, containing the bath variables, in a normal ordered form by positing on it an appropriate Ansatz, only those operators in $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ will survive in $\langle U_{\text{ex}}(t) \rangle$ which have no bath-variables in it. Since $U_{\text{M}}(t)$ in $U(t)$ already has operators in it with system variables only, there will be no loss of generality in our formalism to have in $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ just a 2×2 unit matrix in the system variables as the only term without the bath variables. Thus, $\langle U_{\text{ex}}(t) \rangle = P$ is automatically satisfied. The next section discusses one such choice of Ansatz for $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$.

The pair averages for the bath $\langle f(t_1)f(t_2) \rangle$ play the roles of 'contractions', and the Wick's theorem introduced by us²⁵ allows us to express operators with bath variables as a sum of bath normal products with one, two, ... pair contractions.

The T-ordered and f-normal ordered exponential cumulant representation of $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$:

All the terms of the hamiltonian in eqn. (1) are 2×2 matrices in the system level indices. In eqn. (8), the evolution operator $U(t)$ itself, the external part of it, $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$, and the model part of it, $U_{\text{M}}(t)$ are also all 2×2 matrices. Although $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ is local in time, the various $f(t)$ -variables would appear in it at various times earlier in t under integrals as evident from eqn. (13). Thus, $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ being a power series in $f(t)$, the time-arguments of all the $f(t)$ -variables in it would not generally be just at time t . In this paper, we introduce a new Ansatz for $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ which is in T -ordered form :

$$U_{\text{ex}}(t) = T \left[\exp \left(-i \int_0^t Y(t') dt' \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

where $T[\{\dots\}]$ is a short-hand notation for the series

$$\begin{aligned} U_{\text{ex}}(t) = & 1 - i \int_0^t \{Y(t')\} dt' + (-i)^2 \int_0^t dt' \int_0^{t'} dt'' \\ & \{Y(t')Y(t'')\} + (-i)^3 \int_0^t dt' \int_0^{t'} dt'' \\ & \int_0^{t''} dt''' \{Y(t')Y(t'')Y(t''')\} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$Y(t)$ is itself a power series in both system and the bath variables. The products of $Y(t)$ are to be interpreted as matrix products in the system variables, and the curly brackets imply normal ordering with respect to the bath-variables. In this Ansatz, the successive $Y(t)$ operators in the exponential representation are ordered in time which are subsequently integrated from the right-most argument. $Y(t')$ can be expanded as a series,

$$Y(t') = \sum_n Y_n(t') \quad (16)$$

where $Y_n(t')$ contains n bath-variables in normal order. Moreover, we use the Ansatz for $Y_n(t')$ where time-argument appears only in the amplitude part $\tilde{Y}_n(t')$ of $Y_n(t')$, and f -variables appear at $t' = 0$.

Thus we use the following representation for $Y(t')$:

$$Y(t') = \frac{1}{n!} \{f^n(0)\} \tilde{Y}_n(t') \quad (17)$$

A rationale for such an Ansatz for $Y_n(t)$ can be given by involving Novikov's theorem²⁷, but we do not want to go into the details in this paper.

We have, from eqn. (13),

$$i \frac{\partial U_{\text{ex}}(t)}{\partial t} = [V_1(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t)]_{\text{ex}} - U_{\text{ex}}(t)V_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (18)$$

where we used, $QU_{\text{ex}} = U_{\text{ex}}$.

Substituting the Ansatz, eq. (14), in eq. (18) we have

$$T[Y(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t)] \equiv Y(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t) = [V_1(t)U_{\text{ex}}(t)]_{\text{ex}} - U_{\text{ex}}(t)V_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (19)$$

We now write the product $V_1(t)$ and $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ in eq. (19) in normal order with respect to $f(t)$ using the generalized Wick's theorem²⁵ and use Novikov's theorem²⁷ to get rid of the $f(t)$ -variables. Algebraic equation for $\tilde{Y}_n(t)$ with $n = 1$, i.e. $\tilde{Y}_1(t)$ looks like

$$\tilde{Y}_1(t) = V_1 e^{\lambda t} + \left[(-i)^2 \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \int_0^t dt_1 \tilde{Y}_1(t_1) \int_0^{t_1} dt_2 \tilde{Y}_1(t_2) \right]_1 + \dots - \left[(-i) \int_0^t dt_1 \tilde{Y}_1(t_1) \right] V_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (20)$$

where $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ is given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(t) = V_0(t) - i \frac{\lambda}{2} e^{-\lambda t} V_1 \int_0^t dt_1 \tilde{Y}_1(t_1) \quad (21)$$

$V_0(t)$, $V_1(t)$ are the parts of total interaction potential $V(t)$ without ' $f(t)$ ' and with one ' $f(t)$ ' variable respectively. The quantity $[\dots]_1$ implies that the amplitude part of an operator with one f -variable. Introducing the variables

$\sigma_1(t) [= i \int_0^t \tilde{Y}_1(t') dt']$ and $\Sigma(t) [= -i \tilde{Y}_1(t) \sigma_1(t)]$, we can re-write eqn. (20) as

$$i \frac{\partial \sigma_1(t)}{\partial t} = V_1 e^{\lambda t} + \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \int_0^t dt_1 \Sigma(t_1) - \sigma_1(t) V_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (22)$$

By integrating eqn. (22), we generate $\sigma_1(t)$, which is needed to define $\Sigma(t)$. Also, it is useful to introduce $\Phi(t)$ as

$\int_0^t dt_1 \Sigma(t_1)$, and write,

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(t)}{\partial t} = \Sigma(t) = -i \tilde{Y}_1(t) \sigma_1(t) \quad (23)$$

and integrate eqn. (23) to get $\Phi(t)$. Thus the final set of working equations, under the truncation of $\tilde{Y}_n(t)$ to $n = 1$, read as

$$i \frac{\partial \sigma_1(t)}{\partial t} = V_1 e^{\lambda t} + \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \Phi(t) - \sigma_1(t) V_{\text{eff}}(t) \equiv \tilde{Y}_1(t) \quad (24)$$

$$i \frac{\partial \Phi(t)}{\partial t} = \tilde{Y}_1(t) \sigma_1(t) \quad (25)$$

By solving them starting with $\sigma_1(0) = \Phi(0) = 0$, we get $\sigma_1(t)$ and $\Phi(t)$. We now use the set of eqns. (24) and (25) to get $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ is then given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(t) = V_0(t) + \frac{\lambda}{2} e^{-\lambda t} V_1 \sigma_1(t) \quad (26)$$

Solution of eqn. (10) will eventually yield $U_M(t)$. Since $U_M(t)$ is the effective evolution operator for the system, once $U_M(t)$ is known, all the important bath-averaged quantities can be found out. We will illustrate this with a TLS-bath model which mimics spectral broadening in non-adiabatic nuclear dynamics coupled to a bath. It should be noted that though $Y_1(t)$ involves only one uncontracted active bath variable f , there are many f operators appearing in it which are all pairwise contracted at times earlier than t , as should be evident from the power series in eqn. (20). Thus truncating Y by its first term Y_1 can still be good approximation, than the simple first order approximation $Y(t') \simeq V(t')$, which leads only to the second order cumulant approximation of the Redfield-type of theory²⁸. In the next section, we will present an illustrative application in a realistic situation described by a TLS-bath hamiltonian, and we will explore the efficacy of the approximation $Y(t') \simeq Y_1(t')$.

Illustrative applications : the TLS-bath models

The model :

We are interested in observing the power spectrum in the situation where there is a 'ground' level $|0\rangle$ of the system, which is dynamically noninteracting with excited system levels $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$, except by coupling by a classical electromagnetic field. We take the ground state energy to be zero, the ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are really diagonal energies of the states $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$ relative to the ground state. In addition, the states $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$ are coupled to a bath of OU type involving the bath-variables. The subdynamics of the system is governed by $\langle U(t) \rangle$, and the absorption spectrum depends precisely on this quantity. One can think of this model which mimics the non-adiabatic dynamics of nuclear motion where the vibrational degrees of freedom are modelled as gaussian bath. We assume that only the state $|1\rangle$ is 'photo-active' in the sense that it can be reached from $|0\rangle$ by a electric-dipole operator d and the state $|2\rangle$ is not directly reachable by light and hence is a 'dark' level. The absorption intensity, $I(\Omega)$ is then given by

$$I(\Omega) \propto \int_0^\infty [U_M(t)]_{11} e^{-i\Omega t} dt \quad (27)$$

where $\Omega = \omega - \Delta E$; ω is the Fourier frequency, ΔE is the energy gap between the ground 'inactive' level and the first 'active' level with energy ϵ_1 and $[U_M(t)]_{11}$ is the bath-averaged matrix element of $U(t) \equiv \langle 1 | U(t) | 1 \rangle$ whose real part is proportional to dipole autocorrelation function, $C(t) \equiv \langle 0 | [d_H(t), d_H(0)] | 0 \rangle$, $d_H(t)$ being the dipole operator in Heisenberg representation. The interest in the problem lies in recognizing the signature of memory effects induced by the colored noise in the strong coupling regime, where the system correlation time is of the order of bath correlation time. Since the dynamics leading to the power spectrum involves just the levels $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$, and $|0\rangle$ enters only through the excitation via $\langle 1 | d_H | 0 \rangle$ and $\langle 0 | d_H | 1 \rangle$, the TLS-bath hamiltonian serves as a good prototype model.

The working equations :

From eqn. (1), the general perturbing potential in the interaction representation is given by

$$V_1(t) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g_{ij} f(t) e^{i\Delta_{ij}t} [|i\rangle\langle j|]_I + \sum_{i \neq j=1}^2 \gamma_{ij} e^{i\Delta_{ij}t} [|i\rangle\langle j|]_I \quad (28)$$

where $\Delta_{ij} = \epsilon_i - \epsilon_j$.

In our application, we would keep only the term in Y with one active f -variable, i.e. $Y(t) \sim Y_1(t)$. Actual numerical results will show that this is actually a good approximation for a wide range of coupling constants and the noise parameter, λ . The cluster cumulant equations under such an approximation in long hand is given by

$$i \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{(1)}}{\partial t} = e^{\lambda t} g_{ij} e^{i\Delta_{ij}t} + \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \sum_{k=1}^2 g_{ik} e^{i\Delta_{ik}t} \phi_{kj}^{(2)} + \sum_k \gamma_{ik} e^{i\Delta_{ik}t} \sigma_{kj}^{(1)} - \sum_k \sigma_{ik}^{(1)} [V_{\text{eff}}(t)]_{kj} \quad (29)$$

$$i \frac{\partial \phi_{ij}^{(2)}}{\partial t} = \sum_k \tilde{\gamma}_{ik}^{(1)} \sigma_{kj}^{(1)} \quad (30)$$

with

$$[V_{\text{eff}}(t)]_{ij} = \sum_k g_{ik} e^{i\Delta_{ik}t} \frac{\lambda}{2} e^{-\lambda t} \sigma_{kj}^{(1)} + \gamma_{ij} e^{i\Delta_{ij}t} \quad (31)$$

The equation for the model space evolution operator $U_M(t)$ is driven by $[V_{\text{eff}}(t)]_{ij}$ in eqn. (31) and is given by

$$i \frac{\partial U_M(t)_{ij}}{\partial t} = \sum_k [V_{\text{eff}}(t)]_{ik} [U_M(t)]_{kj} \quad (32)$$

We have solved eqns. (29), (30) and (32) along with eqn.

(31) for a wide range of coupling constants, g and correlation time, τ_c .

The results and discussions :

As explained earlier, we will explore the efficacy of the simplest nonperturbative approximation $Y(t) \simeq Y_1(t)$. To assess the performance of this approximation, we have also generated the numerically exact spectrum by writing $U(t)$ as a power series basis set expansion (BSE) in the bath variables in normal order :

$$U^H(t) = \sum_{i,j;n} U_{ij}^{H(n)}(t) \{f^{(n)}(0)\} |i\rangle\langle j| \quad (33)$$

where $U_{ij}^{H(n)} \equiv \sum_{i,j;n} |i\rangle\langle j|$. Convergence of the solution for U^H is reached when the power spectrum does not change with the addition of more $U^{H(n)}$ terms with greater number n of the bath variables. We have also looked at the accuracy of the results by truncating $U^H(t)$ above after $n = 1$. This is the simplest one-bath variable approximation in the basis expansion of $U^H(t)$, which should be contrasted with the one-bath mode approximation of the $Y(t) : Y(t) \simeq Y_1(t)$. We have also looked analytically at the perturbative cumulant approximation, where $Y(t)$ is approximated by just the first order one-bath component $Y(t) \simeq V(t)$. Because of the bath normal ordering, $Y(t) \simeq V(t)$ provides $V_{\text{eff}}(t)$ upto fourth order in bath variables.

We used two types of bath couplings in our applications : off-diagonal and diagonal. In the former the terms g_{ij} and in the latter only g_{ii} 's are retained. In Figs. 1 and 2, we compare the cluster cumulant (CC) results with that of the BSE using the single bath mode approximation one- f ($n = 1$) and the exact one using the converged nine- f ($n = 9$) for the *off-diagonal* and *diagonal* bath-coupling model respectively with sufficient long noise correlation time, $\tau_c (= 1/\lambda)$. The CC results follow closely the exact results – both with re-

Fig. 1. Plots of the cluster cumulant [CC] results (filled circle) against that of the BSE with one- f ($n = 1$) (filled uptriangle) and the exact one with nine- f ($n = 9$) (filled square) for the parameter $\gamma = 0.6$, $g_{12} = g_{21} = g = 1.0$, $\gamma = 0.0$, $\Delta = 1.0$.

Fig. 2. Plots of the cluster cumulant [CC] results (filled circle) against that of the BSE with one- f ($n = 1$) (filled uptriangle) and the exact one with nine- f ($n = 9$) (filled square) for the parameter $\gamma = 0.3$, $g_{11} = g_{22} = g = 0.3$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\Delta = 1.0$.

spect to peak positions and intensity. In contrast, the one- f BSE results show a spurious distortion of the main peak as well the peak height. Moreover, both the peaks of the spectrum presented in Figs. 1 and 2 are asymmetrically broadened which indicates the non-Markovian signature of the bath and the nonperturbative regime of the bath coupling. Hence, our cluster expansion representation of $U_{\text{ex}}(t)$ with even a low order truncation in the number of the f variable describes the physics much better as compared to a linear BSE with the same number of f variables.

Emergence of the perturbative cumulant approximation :

The TLS-colored bath model was studied earlier by Der and Schumacher¹⁰ in the long time adiabatic limit of t without system coupling terms γ_{ij} and $g_{ij} = |-g_{ij}| = g$, $g_{ij} = 0$. To cross-check our method with that of Der and Schumacher, we set the final limit of integration as infinity and delete terms with γ_{ij} 's. Using eqns. (29), (30), (31) and (32) and putting $\gamma_{ij} = 0$, we obtain the fourth order V_{eff} (taken as an example) as

$$[V_{\text{eff}}]_{11}^{(4)} = \left(\frac{g^2}{2}\right)^2 \frac{\tau_c^2 \Delta}{(1 - i\tau_c \Delta)^3} \quad (34)$$

$$[V_{\text{eff}}]_{22}^{(4)} = -\left(\frac{g^2}{2}\right)^2 \frac{\tau_c^2 \Delta}{(1 + i\tau_c \Delta)^3} \quad (35)$$

for $t \gg \tau_c$, $\Delta = \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$. They agree with the results of Der and Schumacher. Our T -ordered Ansatz thus affords a natural access to the adiabatic results of Der and Schumacher via eqns. (34) and (35).

It is quite clear from the above analysis that in our cluster cumulant framework, even the one- f stochastic approxi-

mation in the external cluster operator ' Y_1 ' is rather good to explain the essential spectral features of the TLS-bath model. The method is superior either to a basis set expansion or to a perturbative approximation under a truncation scheme of the same operator rank.

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